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Abstract: This document provides the SSHOC exploitation plan and defines the project's Key Exploitable Results, the project's value proposition and the joint and individual exploitation routes foreseen. The document is a living document and will be updated again in M40, if relevant.

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Executive Summary

This Exploitation Plan gives an overview of the joint and multiple individual exploitation paths aimed at increasing the impact of all the Key Exploitable Results developed during the SSHOC project lifetime (from January 2019 to April 2022). The Plan is aligned with the contractual obligations defined in articles 28 and 29 of the SSHOC Grant Agreement (No. 823782).

The 33 Key Exploitable Results from SSHOC make available scientific evidence for policy making and enable exploitation through sustained use and/or re-use in other research activities and future funding opportunities. As such, exploitation is instrumental in concretising their value for diverse stakeholder groups, spanning end-users and in the EOSC context, detailing each result, partners involved in its development, and how it will be exploited.

The Exploitation Plan stems from the activities in Work Package 8, especially Task 8.1: “Governance & Sustainability” which handles the overall governance of the SSHOC project, as well as from the continuous consultation processes conducted among the SSHOC Scientific Board and Project Management Board.

Designed as a living record on exploitation rather than an official deliverable, it will feed into SSHOC *D8.1 Governance and Sustainability Roadmap* (M38; February 2022). D8.1 defines the organisational structure needed to safeguard the availability, quality, and maintenance of the results after the project’s funding lifecycle, the conditions for financial sustainability and the measures for implementing the envisaged structure. D8.1 is closely linked to SSHOC *D7.5 Marketplace – Governance* (M36; December 2021) as the guidelines delivered by Task 7.4 detail the roles of various actors and the envisaged workflow for the continuous curation of the Marketplace.

The Exploitation Plan will be updated at the end of the project, when all KERs are delivered and accessible to all stakeholders at M40 (April 2022) of the SSHOC project.

1. Introduction

In the Horizon 2020 Programme increased importance was given to Dissemination and Exploitation, with much more emphasis on impact and thus more value of Research and Innovation funding. The Rules for Participation state clear obligations for beneficiaries in **articles 28 & 29 of the Grant Agreement**¹. The overriding objective is to put funded R&I project results centre stage for the economic and social use of those results and make available scientific evidence in support of policy making.

The EC defines exploitation as the utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating, and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities:

- Make use of the results; recognising exploitable results and their stakeholders.
- Concretise the value and impact of the R&I activity for societal challenges.

Exploitation can be commercial, societal, political, or for improving public knowledge and action. Project partners can exploit results themselves, or facilitate exploitation by others (e.g. by making results available under open licenses).²

The SSHOC exploitation plan aims to increase the impact of all Key Exploitable Results (KERs) developed over the course of the SSHOC project lifetime, from January 2019 to April 2022. The plan looks at the value proposition per stakeholder group as well as the individual and joint exploitation routes for all KERs, based on value propositions for targeted stakeholders.

This document is not an official deliverable, but a living record on exploitation, feeding into SSHOC Task 8.1 sustainability, where the Deliverable 8.1 Governance and Sustainability Roadmap (M38) identifies the organisational structure needed to safeguard the availability, quality and maintenance of the results after the project's funding lifecycle, the conditions for financial sustainability and the actions needed to implement the envisaged structure. And the D7.5 Marketplace – Governance (M36) Guidelines delivered by T7.4 detailing the roles of various actors and the envisaged workflow for the continuous curation of the Marketplace.

The document will be updated at the end of the project, when all KERs are delivered and accessible to all stakeholders at M40 (April 2022) of the SSHOC project.

¹ <https://www.h2020.md/en/horizon-2020-annotated-model-grant-agreements>.

² https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/events/2017-03-01/8_result-dissemination-exploitation.pdf.

2. Methodology

Current document, detailing the SSHOC exploitation plan, was established through a 4-phased approach of identification and input collection from the Project Management Board, KER owners and project partners. The SSHOC value proposition (section 3), provided a solid basis for the phased identification of SSHOC KERs and definition of exploitation paths.

Phase 1: already in M10 (October 2019) of the project, a careful identification of the SSHOC KERs was initiated by WP2, in collaboration with the PMB. This first identification formed the basis for the publication of the SSHOC catalogue of tools and services on the project website, starting to raise awareness of all SSHOC resources to be provided to stakeholders and end-users.

Phase 2: year 2 built on phase 1, in alignment with the services onboarding team of the EOSC Enhance project, when an update on services and tools was performed by partners to identify which services were ready to be onboarded to the EOSC Portal and of course the SSH Open Marketplace. This process led to a final list of 33 KERs in Year 3, identifying which KERs are also usable in domains other than the SSH, and those tailor-made for the SSH community. This list was validated by the PMB.

Phase 3: WP2 and WP1 defined exploitation templates to collect information from each KER owner on:

- Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects.
- Description of the KER.
- Value Proposition for end-user communities.
- Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context.
- Target users and needs, including how they can use the service/tool to meet their needs.
- Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues/dependencies with other service providers/key players.

Note that the value propositions for stakeholders are aligned at all times with the earlier identifications (see section 3) and completed with new insights gathered over the course of the project's lifetime.

Phase 4: Based on the information collected in phase 3, partners contributing to the exploitation of SSHOC KERs were asked to provide their exploitation plans during M33-M36.

3. SSHOC Value Proposition

The table below contains the value proposition of the SSHOC project and its KERs defined per stakeholder group. When filling out the Key Exploitable Results Templates in section 4 you can source the value propositions for end-users and communities from here.

In addition, CLARIN and DARIAH have also defined their value propositions of EOSC for people involved in these two RIs:

- DARIAH: <https://dariahopen.hypotheses.org/1060>; <https://dariahopen.hypotheses.org/1030>
- CLARIN: <https://www.clarin.eu/eosc>

TABLE 2: SSHOC VALUE PROPOSITIONS.

Stakeholders	Potential Benefits to be Derived from SSHOC
Researchers (Research networks and associations)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seamless access to high quality research data. • Easy access to tools and resources to ease data processing and analysis. • Access to secure and trusted repositories for storing data. • Access to tutorials, training materials, user stories. • A self-assessment feature to rate their contribution to research in the humanities.
Research & e-Infrastructures (EOSC Thematic Clusters)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A common governance model for the treatment of thematic data. • Common policies on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ FAIR ◦ data stewardship and harmonisation ◦ quality assessment and impact • Context-driven training. • Increased opportunities to attract users to e-infrastructures. • Increased opportunities to gain visibility and recognition through representation in the EOSC. • Support in CoreTrustSeal certification for repositories.
Research Libraries & Archives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seamless access to data with which to enrich existing data collections. • Enhanced support of research activities through easy access to tools and services with which to boost the visibility and value of data offered to scientific and policy communities. • Access to tutorials, training materials, user stories.

Universities & Research Performing Organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New solutions to test with added value to existing SSH primary data collections. • Data which is easily repurposed and reusable across disciplines. • More data deposited with less effort. • Increased visibility and value of data to the scientific and policy communities. • SSH datasets, tools, and services like in an app store. • Tutorials and training material, user stories.
Policy Making Organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to national and institutional data scalable at European level. • Easier management of IPRs and ethical issues stemming from harmonised data policies. • Access to reports on legislative or interoperability issues affecting data handling across geographical and disciplinary borders.
Research Funding Organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to national and institutional data scalable at European level. • Easier management of IPRs and ethical issues as a result of harmonised data policies.
Private Sector & Industry players	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to promotional and new business opportunities via the SSH Open Marketplace. • A means of interacting with researchers to improve service quality. • Domain specific skilled professionals on data stewardships. • Datasets for commercial use through tailored agreements.
Civil Society and Citizen Scientists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunities to participate in scientific progress via open access to SSH data, services and tools.

4. SSHOC Exploitation Plan

SSHOC counts 33 Key Exploitable Assets, this chapter identifies each of these and defines their exploitation paths, joint and individual.

33 SSHOCing Key Exploitable Results to support your research in SSH and Beyond

FIGURE 1: INFOGRAPHIC 33 KERS

4.1. SSHOC Key Exploitable Results Overview

This section identifies all SSHOC Key Exploitable Results and maps them according to usability for research in the SSH or upgradable to applications for other disciplines. For each KER the leading partner is indicated.

TABLE 3: SSHOC KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS.

No	SSHOC KER Can be upgraded to applications for other disciplines	Leading partner
1	The SSH Open Marketplace may serve as a best practice for other (EOSC-related) thematic catalogues & marketplaces.	DARIAH
2	CLARIN Switchboard (support to connect data and tools).	CLARIN
3	Virtual Collection Registry (users can select and save data from different repositories into an individual 'shopping bag', share with colleagues or publish).	CLARIN
4	The cultural heritage Aïoli-platform for 3D-annotation of artefacts.	CNRS
5	The Web Panel Sample Service (WPSS) for cross-national surveys and panels.	ESS
6	FAIR SSH data citation prototype should also work for other disciplines (To decide if SSH or multidisciplinary).	CNRS
7	League of Data	CESSDA, TRUST-IT
No	SSHOC KER Will serve the SSH community directly	Leading partner
8	SSH Training Discovery Toolkit: a curated registry of training resources (links to existing SSH training hubs, materials, events, reports) for trainers.	KNAW (DANS)
9	SSH Trainer Directory: A directory of SSH trainers as product to support the SSH training community	KNAW (DANS)
10	SSH Conversion Hub: Metadata conversion services between the most relevant metadata formats.	CESSDA
11	The Automatic Verification Tool to verify translations of survey questions.	SHARE

12	SSHOCro: Social Science and Humanities Reference Ontology	FORTH
13	ARIADNE-plus for improved archaeological data management.	UoY-ADS
14	Knowledge Graphs in Electoral Studies to bring together structured and unstructured data.	UNOTT, SWC
15	The Ethnic and Migrant Minority Survey Registry (1000+ surveys from 30+ (EU) countries) to easily search for and learn about existing quantitative surveys in this domain.	Sciences Po
16	The [MCSQ]: The Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires	ESS
17	Repository service for SSH (Dataverse)	DANS
18	ADS Guides to Good Practice	UoY-ADS
19	Multilingual Terminologies (stored at ILC CLARIN centre, some of these may go to surveycodings.org)	CNR
20	surveycodings.org, hosting all SSHOC Task 3.2 produced ontologies	SHARE/CENT ERDATA
21	RESTORE	CNR
22	Dataset: Investigating the effects of machine translation and post-editing in survey translation. This is a dataset containing two experiments conducted in the language pairs English-German and English-Russian. Includes linguistic data and human (questionnaires' data).	ESS
23a	Improved and FAIR data Repositories: New ESS data repository (WP 5 work on Setting up and populating a new ESS repository)	ESS

23b	<p>Improved and FAIR data Repositories: SSHOC Trusted Repositories (WP 8 work on trust and quality assurance by supporting data repositories in their journey to CoreTrustSeal certification):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CESSDA repositories accessed via CESSDA data catalogue (CROSSDA and SASD) 2. CLARIN-LV 3. SB/CLARIN Repository (Språkbanken Text CLARIN Repository) 4. Corpus OVI dell'italiano antico 5. DAIS - Digital Archive of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts 6. DARIAH-DE Repository 7. Digital Library of University of Maribor 8. Digital Repository of Scientific Institutes 9. Historic Graves 10. Lithuanian Data Archive for Social Sciences and Humanities (LiDA) 11. mdw Repository 12. NAKALA 13. Sciences Po, Center for Socio-Political Data (CDSP) 	CESSDA
23c	Improved and FAIR data Repositories: SHARE survey data improved and enriched by adding Dry Blood Spot samples data (DBS) and the collection of objective physical activity data by using accelerometry.	SHARE
24a	SSH Communities: Training Community A worldwide community of trainers in the SSH, who collaborate to improve their professional capabilities, expertise and resources.	KNAW (DANS)
24b	SSH Communities: Ethnic Minorities and Migration Data Community	Sciences Po
24c	SSH Communities: Election Studies Data Community	UNOTT
24d	SSH Communities: Heritage Science Data Community	CNR
24e	SSH Communities: Religious Studies Data Community	INFAI , FSCIRE (RESILIENCE)
24f	SSH Communities: Historic Economic Data Community	EEP PSE, SAFE, Uantwerp (EURHISFIRM)
24g	SSH Communities: Upcoming: Child & Youth Wellbeing Data Community	MMU (COORDINATE)

25	Audio Survey Experiment	KNAW (NIDI)
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4.2. Joint Exploitation Plan

The joint exploitation path is based on several pillar activities, all contributing to the increasing impact of the SSHOC 33 KERs and ultimately their sustainability as addressed in T8.1. Below we outline the pillars and their status at M36.

Over the course of the SSHOC project lifetime, the consortium has been positioned as the point of reference for SSH in EOSC. The growing consortium has agreed to continue to collaborate under the **SSHOC Memorandum of Understanding**. The overall objective is to establish the SSH Open Cluster as an instrument of further collaboration between different SSH community stakeholders taking an active role in promoting quality and impact of SSH within the European Research Area and beyond. The purpose of the memorandum is to enhance mutual interaction, build upon and expand existing synergies and expertise, and support sharing of know-how in all areas of common interest.

The memorandum deals with the following broad areas of common interest: support to the SSH research communities, optimised use of existing resources, identification and response to challenges, visibility and branding in the area of SSH, high-level interactions with the EC and other EU bodies, advocate SSH research community interests in European and international research context, single contact point in collaboration with European and global scientific organisations, and finally, visibility, impact, and sustainability of the SSH domain and its stakeholders with coordinated representation to the general public, national governments, non-EU countries and global players.

To showcase this unity beyond the project lifetime, the continuous growth of the original consortium which started off in January 2019 and its positioning in EOSC, the consortium is expanding on its already established project branding with a **sustainable branding as SSH Open Cluster**.

FIGURE 2: SSH OPEN CLUSTER BRANDING, EXPANDING ON THE FAMILIAR LOOK & FEEL OF SSHOC

FIGURE 3: SAMPLES OF TAILORED AND SUSTAINABLE BRANDING FOR ALL SSH OPEN CLUSTER TOOLS & SERVICES

Of course, the **onboarding of SSHOC resources to the SSH Open Marketplace** supports a joint exploitation of these KERs, making them available to the SSH research Community as described in *D7.5 Marketplace – Governance*³. A result of the work carried out as part of SSHOC Task 7.4 - “Governance: Population, Curation & Sustainability of the SSH Open Marketplace”, itself embedded in WP7 - “Creating the SSH Open Marketplace” of the SSHOC project. It supports the creation of the SSH Open Marketplace: a discovery portal crafted for the SSH research community, offering contextualised solutions to diverse research enquiries, at every step of a researcher’s data life cycle. Also considering the work done under WP8, especially Task 8.1 “Governance & Sustainability” handling the overall governance of the SSHOC project, and the consultation processes conducted among the SSHOC Scientific and Project Management Boards.

In addition, and as mentioned in section 2, **SSHOC has collaborated with the EOSC Enhance project to onboard project resources to the EOSC Portal**, making them widely available to the EOSC User Base.

In April 2021, the EOSC Future project kicked off, where SSHOC, in collaboration with the other 4 thematic clusters is involved to perform cross-domain Science Projects, and tap into its already strong user community (see deliverable *D2.2 Preliminary Report on User Communities’ Engagement*⁴). **SSHOC’s involvement in EOSC Future**, continues work already set in motion in the project lifetime of cross-cluster collaboration and contribution to the EOSC.

4.3. Individual Exploitation Plans

SSHOC partners have collaboratively collected all information needed to define individual exploitation paths per KER. Each subsection below indicates the following per KER:

- Partners contributing to its development, operational and/or training aspects.
- Description of the KER.
- Value Proposition for end-user communities.
- Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context.
- Target users and needs, including how they can use the service/tool.
- Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues/dependencies with other service providers/key players.
- Partners’ exploitation plans.

³ Clara Petitfils, Suzanne Dumouchel, Nicolas Larrousse, Edward J. Gray, Laure Barbot, Arnaud Roi, Matej Ďurčo, Klaus Illmayer, Stefan Buddenbohm, & Tomasz Parkola. (2021). *D7.5 Marketplace - Governance*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5608487>.

⁴ Marieke Willems, Tracey Biller, Filomena Minichiello, & Veronika Heider. (2021). *SSHOC D2.2 Preliminary Report on User Communities’ Engagement (V1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4655994>.

4.3.1. Exploitation – KER #1 SSH Open Marketplace

KER Name: SSH Open Marketplace Leading partner: DARIAH	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	<p>Developed within SSHOC WP7, the SSH Open Marketplace is mainly created by the following partners:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DARIAH ERIC • DARIAH/OEAW • DARIAH/PSNC • CESSDA ERIC • CLARIN ERIC • DARIAH/UGOE • TRUST-IT • SWC • CNRS • CNR • FORTH <p>Other WPs and partners have contributed to the tests, creation of content, curation sprints or dissemination, thus fostering early adoption of the service, which is one of the prerequisites for its exploitation.</p>
Description of the KER	<p>Discoverability and findability of research services and products are essential to enable sharing and re-use of workflows and methodologies. To support SSH researchers in their research methods and at every step of the research data lifecycle, the SSH Open Marketplace pools and harmonises their key:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • tools and services • datasets • training materials • workflows • and publications <p>..... and makes them available and contextualised in a discovery portal.</p>
Value Proposition for end-user communities	<p>Thanks to the SSH Open Marketplace, SSH researchers can:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - gain access to useful and well curated resources - find and discover new digital methods - easily understand and assess usefulness of a resource thanks to the contextualisation provided between the items of the catalogue - promote their work, e.g. by adding information about the tool or workflow they develop - actively involve in the SSH community data curation routines, becoming basic contributor or advanced curator.

<p>Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context</p>	<p>The SSH Open Marketplace is a key element for the SSH branch of the EOSC. As a thematic catalogue, it is an entry point to the EOSC for SSH researchers for whom the wider EOSC environment may not seem relevant. The SSH Open Marketplace is also an opportunity for other “research outputs” than services to be visible in the EOSC.</p> <p>For policy makers, the SSH Open Marketplace can also serve as a tool to gain an overview of the existing resources landscape in SSH (e.g., it can be used to conduct gap analysis of resources used and provided by the community).</p>
<p>Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool</p>	<p>Target users are primarily SSH researchers. Based on previous projects and continuous efforts to collect users' needs (see SSHOC D7.1 or MS43 report), one of the major assets of the service is the contextualisation: context between resources is key!</p> <p>Thanks to its user-friendly design and to the contextualisation layers added to this registry, users can find resources serendipitously, the same way as browsing through open shelves of big libraries. For instance, a researcher looking for a textual analysis tool will find not only a very comprehensive treatment of the most pertinent tools in current use, but also associated resources such as user guides, reviews of the tools by fellow researchers, and perhaps even a case study on how to use such tools.</p> <p>The Workflow content type in the SSH Open Marketplace is also an answer to the richer approach to contextualisation that is particularly important to the SSH community. Workflows include a sequence of steps to describe how to perform a task within the research data lifecycle and linking useful resources to each step.</p> <p>See the video: SSH Open Marketplace - explained the easy way</p>
<p>Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players</p>	<p>Barriers to exploitation identified are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of uptake by the research community. To overcome this risk, previous experiences in Digital Humanities have been incorporated, quality requirements for the content set and a mix of incentives and rewards is planned to support community contributions in the post-project era. - Lack of (additional) resources among the partners to ensure continuous quality of content and continued growth of the service. - Interoperability issues to ensure the EOSC incorporation. <p>Sustainability and governance plans (T7.4) have been developed, next to the exploitation plans below to limit the risks and deliver a solid framework for exploitation.</p>

<p>Exploitation plan per partner</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DARIAH: DARIAH strategic plan includes commitment to the SSH Open Marketplace; regular briefings to DARIAH National Coordinators are organised; an integration of DARIAH Service catalogue with the SSH Open Marketplace has been developed; the SSH Open Marketplace is featured at DARIAH events; possibilities to feature the Marketplace in DARIAH funding calls are under discussions; regular communication campaigns on DARIAH channels are organised. • PSNC: 1) Use the SSH Open Marketplace (if agreed with leading partners) to promote tools and services that will be built in the national DARIAH-PL project (https://lab.dariah.pl/). The intention is to expose information about DARIAH-PL infrastructure (e.g. API, export file) so that it is possible to aggregate it by the SSH Open Marketplace and then present it on the SSH Open Marketplace portal. 2) Further develop the DACE aggregation engine (being base for SSH Open Marketplace aggregation routines) and promote/use it in other projects, e.g. related to cultural heritage data aggregation (e.g. national and regional aggregators). • CLARIN ERIC: The CLARIN ERIC Strategy 2021-2023 includes commitment to align with the SSH Open Marketplace; CLARIN aims at improving the discoverability of tools provided by the CLARIN centres and the thematic services offered by the SSH Open Marketplace. Any developments related to the SSH Open Marketplace are featured (when suitable) on the monthly newsletter, at CLARIN organised events and on CLARIN's social media channels. • ACDH-CH OEAW: The institute's mission is to support and foster digital methods in the humanities community. As part of this commitment and in line with the Digital Humanities Austria strategy, it is hosting a number of infrastructure services on behalf of the research infrastructures CLARIN and DARIAH, like Vocabulary Service, ARCHE repository, as well as especially the SSH Open Marketplace. This includes both ensuring the running of the services technically, as well as continuous content curation. • Trust-IT: as per its involvement in EOSC related projects as well as the Horizon Results Booster, Trust-IT will continue to raise awareness on the SSH Open Marketplace and continue fostering its uptake in the EOSC Future project. • CESSDA ERIC: CESSDA's mission is to provide access to research data in social sciences as part of the EOSC. Data must be accompanied by tools and training resources that enable researchers to fully utilise the data within and beyond the domain. For CESSDA, the SSH Open Marketplace provides the ideal discovery platform to achieve this goal. Therefore CESSDA is committed to ensure its resources are included in the marketplace and to continue promoting it as a central access point.
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4.3.2. Exploitation – KER #2 CLARIN Switchboard

KER Name: CLARIN Switchboard Leading partner: CLARIN	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	CLARIN, EKUT, CNR, UGOE, OAEW, DAI, LIBER
Description of the KER	<p>CLARIN's original Language Resource Switchboard matches language resources with suitable processing tools, automatically guiding researchers to the right language analysis application. SSHOC has extended the Switchboard to provide support for broader data types used in Humanities and Social Sciences research, e.g. tabular data with geographic coordinates. Additional information directed at a broader SSH audience was created and a workshop directed at SSH researcher organised to test and obtain further feedback about the Switchboard use in researcher workflows.</p> <p>See D3.8 for a broad overview and discussion of all aspects related to Switchboard and VCR.</p>
Value Proposition for end-user communities	CLARIN offers this service to the research community, although from a practical perspective due to the integrated services the SSH users can profit most. CLARIN also offers an option for communities to, after some checking, have new services added to the Switchboard. For the purpose of collaboration with the SSH in SSHOC, EKUT currently operates a SSHOC version of the Switchboard which allows fast track integration of new services and new features.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	In principle this service can be of use to the broader research community, and although its operation and maintenance is now better placed within SSH/CLARIN domain it should be integrated and also provided via EOSC channels.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	<p>The Switchboard, although developed within a language research data-oriented community, has open use cases from other data domains, particularly the humanities discussed and implemented in SSHOC. This discussion was documented in a separate publication with regard to the SSH Open Marketplace and with focus on the Switchboard in general in D3.8.</p> <p>Particularly the discussion with stakeholders and research infrastructure initiatives like CESSDA, DARIAH, and E-HRIS lead to promising use-cases on how to open up the Switchboard for other SSH data and research domains. Also use-cases with an unfavourable cost-benefit-ratio have been identified. Both categories are important for an informed development road map for the Switchboard.</p>

<p>Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players</p>	<p>With moderate uptake and change-requests no specific barriers are expected with regard to service provisioning and maintenance. However, increased uptake could encounter the following issues:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lack of a software sharing ‘culture’ for some partners e.g. organisations not easily being able to use external code (see D3.8 p13) • lack of outreach effort to open up further user communities and data domains. However at the same time that would also have consequences for the available operational and maintenance resources.
<p>Exploitation plan per partner</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CLARIN ERIC maintains the core software and operates the CLARIN production services of both Switchboard and VCR. • EKUT will continue caring (on a best effort basis) for the developed extensions of Switchboard beyond those integrated in the CLARIN production version that are useful for a wider community as in the collaboration with DARIAH-DE. • OEAW will maintain the integration of Switchboard and VCR in ARCHE. • DARIAH UGOE: It is very likely, that the SSHOC-derived cooperation with the developers of both services will be continued either within the CLARIAH domain and/or the NFDI domain, the German National Research Data Infrastructure. • CNR and KNAW(DANS) These partners have integrated code in the SSHOC DataVerse source code that facilitates using the Switchboard from DataVerse.

4.3.3. Exploitation – KER #3 Virtual Collection Registry

<p style="text-align: center;">KER Name: Virtual Collection Registry Leading partner: CLARIN</p>	
<p>Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects</p>	<p>CLARIN, EKUT, CNR, UGOE, OAEW, DAI, LIBER, SND</p>
<p>Description of the KER</p>	<p>The Virtual Collection Registry (VCR) enables researchers to create, register and manage virtual collections that are integrated, coherent sets of links to distributed resources of interest for the virtual collection creator and user. Each virtual collection comes with a persistent identifier and FAIR metadata. The registry can be easily accessed via federated login and API.</p> <p>The collection metadata is openly available and accessible via the Virtual Language Observatory.</p> <p>See D3.8 for a broad overview and discussion of all aspects related to Switchboard and VCR.</p>

Value Proposition for end-user communities	The VCR is a service that CLARIN provides for the benefit of researchers, especially those from SSH, and can be used to optimise their research workflow and support FAIR data practices.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	CLARIN currently offers this service to the broad research community. In view of the very general nature of this service, CLARIN looks for collaboration with general infrastructure organisations operating in EOSC that would also be willing to support this service. The VCR should be integrated and also provided via EOSC channels.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	The Virtual Collection Registry, although developed within a language research data oriented community, has open use cases from other data domains, particularly the humanities, cultural and social sciences. Broadening and increasing uptake of the VCR by other user communities and data domains in the SSHOC context has been documented in D3.8 , which can inform the development roadmap of the VCR.
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	An effort should be made to communicate ‘proper-use’ with the users, since potential over-use of this service in certain unintended workflows could lead to problematic situations.
Exploitation plan per partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CLARIN ERIC maintains the core software and operates the CLARIN production services of both Switchboard and VCR. • EKUT will maintain and operate additional web-services such as CMDIexplorer and Weblicht-batch that are required for the realisation of some of the VCR use-cases. • OEAW will maintain the integration of Switchboard and VCR in ARCHE. • SND: in order to participate in the VCR shopping-basket use-case scenario, SND integrates the VCR in the landing pages of their online catalogue, which will be supported as long as thought useful. • DARIAH UGOE (CLARIAH-DE): The Virtual Collection Registry is of interest for the user communities of CLARIAH-DE, which serves as German hub for the service provision for language- and humanities related users from the academia. It is likely that the SSHOC-derived cooperation with the developers of both services will be continued within CLARIAH-DE and/or within the NFDI, the German National Research Data Infrastructure. DARIAH UGOE will maintain integration of Switchboard and VCR in the agreed DARIAH-DE tools e.g. TextGrid, and the documentation developed in SSHOC to guide and support researchers using Switchboard and VCR.

4.3.4. Exploitation – KER #4 cultural heritage Aioli-platform

KER Name: cultural heritage Aioli-platform Leading partner: CNRS	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	CNRS
Description of the KER	An innovative web service for the reality-based 3D annotation and large-scale collaborative documentation of heritage artefacts. The existing Aioli platform has been significantly upgraded in terms of technical robustness, the collaboration framework was provided, the management of controlled vocabularies, and compatibility with CIDOC-CRM was established.
Value Proposition for end-user communities	Aioli will allow the wide community (Humanities, Material Science, Engineering, ...) working on Heritage Science to experiment new ways for gathering, sharing and publishing semantically rich 3D models of heritage artefacts.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	Given the spectrum of disciplines involved in the heritage science, and given the innovative nature of the Aioli platform (providing users with a multi-layers annotation environment also including the link with controlled vocabularies), EOSC will be an ideal framework for fostering the emergence of a new generation of digital resources coming from a collaborative, European and multidisciplinary endeavour.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	Aioli is addressed to the scientific and professional community working on the study, conservation and restoration of cultural heritage. Needs include the 3D and 4D digitisation of artworks, architectural elements, buildings and archaeological sites, as well as their geometric analysis (e.g. measurements) and the structuring of heterogeneous data (e.g. texts, illustrations, videos, etc...).
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	Given its current degree of technological maturity, and its innovative and experimental nature, Aioli is today used by a very small community interested in testing its features. The transition to a wider community of users will introduce new issues concerning the follow-up, in terms of technical (e.g. storing capabilities) and human resources. (e.g. support for users).
Exploitation plan per partner	CNRS is working on the definition of a plan for upcoming exploitation within the framework of the FSP (French Heritage Science Foundation) and the E-RIHS (European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science). In particular, Aioli is already included in federative projects for integrating tools, services and communities for the digital documentation of Cultural Heritage, such as the Notre-Dame Scientific action (CNRS/Ministry of Culture) - linked to the HumaNum very large facility, the EquipeX+ ESPADON project (large national equipment for the french Heritage Science community), as well as for three research & innovation projects recently submitted in collaboration with European partners.

4.3.5. Exploitation –KER #5 Web Panel Sample Service (WPSS) for cross-national surveys and panels

KER Name: Web Panel Sample Service (WPSS) Leading partner: ESS ERIC	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	ESS ERIC and Sciences Po
Description of the KER	This task has produced a secure sample management web application coupled with a survey platform (a Qualtrics dedicated license) to meet the needs of high-quality cross-national probability-based online panels. The service is called WPSS (Web Panel Sample Service).
Value Proposition for end-user communities	<p>The service is multilingual by design, it can accommodate cross-national samples using as many languages/language variants as desired. The language is set on participant level.</p> <p>Contacts with panellists is multi-mode; invites and reminders can be sent by email or short text message as desired.</p> <p>The tool is based on a distributed model where several roles collaborate (questionnaire developers, translators, sample managers, survey headquarters). Access to data is defined on a need-to-know basis, preserving confidentiality.</p> <p>The survey lifecycle is centrally managed; survey publication and messages are precisely synchronized across the whole sample.</p> <p>An extensive online Wiki is available for the public.</p>
Value proposition for EOOSC and the wider policy context	This tool has been designed as a response to the lack of available reliable platforms that would meet the needs of high-quality cross-national probability-based online panels. This is especially in line with the aim of the EOOSC, and will be available on the EOOSC marketplace.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	WPSS can be used in various studies where managing a sample and distributing surveys is needed, for the SSH and many other domains. It is a web only service, easy to deploy by design (containers). Adoption by users is facilitated by an online wiki.
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	WPSS relies on the availability of a Qualtrics instance with several options (EU data center, API, data isolation, data encryption, contact deduplication ...).
Exploitation plan per partner	Sciences Po and ESS ERIC: WPSS is already in use by the CRONOS-2 project (funded by the EC until June 2023 as ESS-SUSTAIN-2). The software will be maintained for two years after the end of the SSHOC grant. In the framework of ESS-SUSTAIN-2, twelve research teams from the participating countries will be using the tool, being a first audience and potential users. Sciences Po and ESS ERIC will continue to showcase the tool and its outputs to the research community. The project team intends to release the main software component of WPSS as open source and available under an open license to facilitate its reuse by the research community.

4.3.6. Exploitation –KER #6 FAIR SSH data citation prototype

KER Name: FAIR SSH data citation prototype Leading partner: CNRS	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	CNR-ISTI, CNRS-HumaNum,
Description of the KER	<p>The FAIR SSH Data Citation prototype is a software tool designed and developed in the SSHOC project to support the process of creating FAIR SSH citations. As described in SSHOC Deliverable 3.5, the main steps to build a FAIR SSH citation are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take the citation string (PID a minima, author etc.) or existing information. • Process the string to put it in a standard shape. • Provide an access to the Digital Object. • Aggregate other information from different sources for instance based on the PID. • Add semantic annotations with some tools from human and machine. • Create a citation viewer. • Provide an API to “disseminate” FAIR citation. <p>The prototype provides functionalities to retrieve and collect metadata related to the cited Digital Object and enables (i) users to visualise the metadata using a web based GUI and (ii) software agents to download the metadata as a JSON object. The retrieved metadata, then, could be used to annotate the original citation.</p>
Value Proposition for end-user communities	The SSH FAIR Data Citation prototype allows researchers to rapidly check the metadata of a given source, as well as ensuring that the metadata remains machine actionable. In its current status, it is a valuable tool to do research on citations, it can show what is cited, how it is cited, and we expect it to be useful for end users by the end of the project. The two components (API & User interface) can be used separately.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	This tool has been designed to help accommodate the growing practice of FAIR Data Citation in the SSH community. It was received favourably by a round table of experts in May 2021, as a means to allow SSH researchers, engineers, and technicians to rapidly treat citations in a machine-actionable way.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	Researchers and digital humanities engineers can use the platform, both to rapidly check a resource’s metadata from a PID and ensuring that their metadata is machine actionable. As well, users can download this data as a JSON object, allowing for further treatment via machine or human actions.

Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	The Prototype is at a TRL readiness level of 4 or 5. It has produced interesting results but will need development beyond the framework of SSHOC to reach a higher TRL.
Exploitation plan per partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CNRS - Promote the Citation Tool among research engineers in the SSH in France. • CNR - Code will still be available via institutional repositories (GitLab) and documentation added to institutional depository. • CLARIN - Investigate integration of some of the software into burgeoning CLARIN Digital Object Gateway (DOG) platform.

4.3.7. Exploitation –KER #7 League of Data

KER Name: League of Data Leading partner: Trust-IT, CESSDA	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	CESSDA, ADP, LIBER, Trust-IT
Description of the KER	<p>A pilot gamification of the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide that can be used in the SSH and beyond, among partners and the wider EOSC ecosystem. The gamification service should be applicable for other tools which will be made clear once the gamification platform is built. SSHOC LoD (League of Data) platform shall support and motivate researchers to publish their research data, by providing guidance for the publishing process. Researchers will be able to test their knowledge, run a checklist on their Data Management Plan and data publishing, and get in touch with peers. To increase the attractiveness of sharing data, the LoD will implement gamification mechanisms and elements. The use of gamification is intended to make users feel more comfortable performing certain tasks, thus increasing their motivation and engagement regarding the task. With respect to the preparation of research data for its publication, LoD shall convert an otherwise strenuous and opaque process, including lots of internet search and the study of bulky standards, into an exciting and joyful adventure which provides unknown opportunities and possibilities. User communities will be engaged and onboarded to the SSHOC community, SSH researchers will be developing skills and knowledge on research data management, and Consortium will provide a sustainable service for researchers in the EOSC ecosystem.</p>
Value Proposition for end-user communities	<p>The use of gamification of the data management process is intended to make users feel more comfortable performing certain tasks, thus increasing their motivation and engagement regarding the task. With respect to the preparation of research data for its publication, LoD shall convert an otherwise strenuous and opaque process, including lots of internet search and the study of bulky standards, into an exciting and joyful adventure which provides unknown opportunities and possibilities.</p>

Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	With respect to the preparation of research data for its publication, LoD shall convert an otherwise strenuous and opaque process, including lots of internet search and the study of bulky standards, into an exciting and joyful adventure which provides unknown opportunities and possibilities. Ensuring alignment with current policies and EOSC practices in place. The LoD is valuable for the SSH research community and beyond.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	Early career researchers Trainers
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	The LoD will not be ready until M36 of SSHOC, therefore it will need to be picked up in future promotion and training activities of CESSDA, LIBER, Trust-IT and the SSH Open Cluster.
Exploitation plan per partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CESSDA: promotion among 22 national members and among ESFRI connections and the EOSC Future project. • ADP: promote in the national research community, CESSDA Training Working Group and TRIPLE project • Trust-IT: promote in the EOSC ecosystem and in relevant Research Data communities and initiatives. Showcase the added value of a serious game for research data management via its network.

4.3.8. Exploitation –KER #8 SSH Training Discovery Toolkit

KER Name: SSH Training Discovery Toolkit Leading partner: KNAW (DANS)	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	KNAW (DANS), LIBER, CESSDA/GESIS, CESSDA/UKDS, CLARIN/UL-FF, UCL
Description of the KER	The SSH Training Discovery Toolkit (“Toolkit” in short) is an inventory of various learning and training materials that trainers of different disciplines in the SSH can use to find materials for re-use in their own training. The Toolkit links to a variety of materials available through various sources on topics including Open Science, Research Data Management, and didactics, but also specific topics that are relevant to multiple disciplines, like text encoding and spatial data. While the Toolkit does not store the resources themselves, it has access links that redirect the user to the resource in question. The Toolkit is a work in progress and has more than 180 items from 78 different sources on the above-mentioned topics for better development and implementation of training activities.
Value Proposition for end-user communities	The Training Discovery Toolkit is an inventory of training materials relevant for trainers in the social science community. It allows trainers to find materials for re-use in one environment.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	The Training Discovery Toolkit can be used to find training materials relevant to the field of SSH. It has curated metadata on training resources which can be combined with other initiatives to make training materials more discoverable and enable reuse and knowledge exchange.

Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	The Toolkit was developed to make existing training materials more discoverable. Trainers can use it to find materials they can reuse in their training activities.
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	The Toolkit was developed and curated during the SSHOC project. As of today, it is unclear whether and how materials will be updated in the future. Hosting and curation effort as well as initial funding or agreement on this needs to be stated to enable sustainability after the SSHOC project. There are optional scenarios explored such as Austrian Academy of Science keeps hosting and curation as a shared effort by ERICs, perhaps with involvement of the editorial team of the SSH Open marketplace.
Exploitation plan per partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See above for optional scenarios. • KNAW (DANS): Promote the Toolkit as a resource to find training materials. • LIBER: Promote the Toolkit among its members as a resource to find training materials, as well as to contribute their training material

4.3.9. Exploitation –KER #9 SSH Trainer Directory

KER Name: SSH Trainer Directory Leading partner: KNAW (DANS)	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	CESSDA/GESIS, KNAW (DANS), LIBER, Trust-IT
Description of the KER	The Trainer Directory is an inventory of trainers in the field of SSH that gives an overview of their expertise and training they provide.
Value Proposition for end-user communities	The directory can be used by people looking for a trainer to find one that may suit their needs. It can also be valuable for trainers to increase their visibility and promote their services.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	Training is an important aspect for the EOSC and the directory increases the visibility of trainers who offer training on particular topics.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	Individuals/organisations interested in organising trainings for particular audiences and/or topics can find a trainer in this directory. Trainers can offer their services and promote their work but can also contact colleague trainers to collaboratively offer trainings.

Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	The directory was developed and curated during the SSHOC project. As of today, it is unclear whether and how information will be updated in the future. The website is planned to be maintained within three years of project completion. Beyond this timeframe there are optional scenarios explored such as the EOSC Future project taking over, or interest by ERICs, SSHOC partners, Triple/OPERAs, community of practice of training coordinators in taking over.
Exploitation plan per partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See above for possible scenarios. • KNAW (DANS): Including its own trainers in the directory to promote KNAW(DANS)'s training activities. Discuss with the EOSC Future project to include a trainer directory (not only limited to SSH) building on the experiences of the SSHOC project. • LIBER: Include LIBER trainers in the directory, as well as promote the directory among LIBER members and assist them with including their trainers should there be interest. • Trust-IT: foster onboarding trainers as well as use of the directory to connect to trainers via Trust-IT's involvement in EOSC related projects and initiatives, as well as raising awareness with relevant research projects via the Horizons Results Booster.

4.3.10. Exploitation –KER #10 SSH Conversion Hub

KER Name: SSH Conversion Hub Leading partner: CESSDA FSD	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	CESSDA/FSD, CESSDA/SND, CESSDA/UKDS, CLARIN ERIC, CLARIN/EKUT, DARIAH/OEAW, ISTI/CNR, DARIAH.it/CNR, FORTH
Description of the KER	A registry of (meta)data conversion services and solutions featuring the most relevant SSH (meta)data formats as recommended by SSHOC and encompassing links to services. Conversion tools created by Task 3.5 will be included in the Conversion Hub.
Value Proposition for end-user communities	Easy access to tools and resources to facilitate data processing and analysis
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	Interoperability is important for building EOSC and the Conversion Hub will increase interoperability for its part.

Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	Conversion Hub can be used by researchers looking for solutions to do metadata or data format conversions between what can be considered the major recommended metadata standards and data formats used in the SSH. Each SSH community has its own established traditions and customs that may cause interoperability issues with other communities. The existing diversity needs to be accepted since in most cases, the different formats and practices make good sense.
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	The Conversion Hub was developed and curated during the SSHOC project. As of today, it is unclear whether and how information will be updated in the future. Scenarios and recommendations are included in D3.6.
Exploitation plan per partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DARIAH/OEAW: hosting the technology; • See D3.6 for scenarios about maintenance of content.

4.3.11. Exploitation –KER #11 Automatic Verification Tool

KER Name: Automatic Verification Tool Leading partner: SHARE ERIC	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	SHARE-ERIC
Description of the KER	<p>The Automatic Verification Tool (AVT) enables the user to verify translations using Bilingual Word Embeddings and to report to the translators a set of translated questions to be re-checked.</p> <p>The AVT imports the questions and makes use of a trained Bilingual Word Embeddings model. It generates the 10 best foreign language translations of each English word.</p> <p>If one of the best translations is in the human foreign language translation it marks the word pair as matched. By measuring the number of matched word pairs. It estimates the translation quality. It stores the translation quality scores and reports them to the user.</p>
Value Proposition for end-user communities	Efficiency gains during the verification of the translations of questionnaires in a multi-country setting.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	European survey projects might add AVT to their toolbox increasing the quality of their data collection with a slight increase in operational costs.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	The AVT aims at improving the verification step for the coordinator of the translation procedures in a multi-country survey project. The AVT processes simple text files imported by the user and provides output easily readable by common text editors.
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	None.

Exploitation plan per partner	SHARE-ERIC plans to make use of the AVT during the verification of future SHARE waves. SHARE-ERIC plans to promote the AVT among other survey projects in Europe.
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4.3.12. Exploitation –KER #12 SSHOCro

KER Name: SSHOCro Leading partner: FORTH	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	FORTH
Description of the KER	SSHOCro is a workflow model which aims to describe the whole data life cycle in social sciences and humanities research including both the generations and the processing of the data.
Value Proposition for end-user communities	<p>SSHOCro proposes an ontological model and Resource Description Framework (RDF) schema to be used as a top-level ontology for organizing knowledge and information found distributed across various primary sources of information in the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC).</p> <p>It aspires to provide a semantic interoperability framework for the description of the SSHOC data lifecycle, by offering a conceptual model that can be used to (re)describe at a generic level the real-world lifecycle of creating, finding and using data –amongst other actions –as it actually takes place in the various domains of Social Sciences and Humanities.</p> <p>In practical terms, the use of such a model and schema for the research community is twofold:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. It can be applied as a standard to be used in the step of devising and implementing metadata capture scheme for tracking the data lifecycle in individual projects, institutions and disciplines; 2. It can also be used to map, transform and integrate existing data across projects, institutions and disciplines into interoperable pools of information for reuse and exploitation.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	The SSHOCro model describes the processes identified in and documented by most scientific research workflow procedures. In this context, it provides appropriate classes for the different stages of the research workflows described in individual projects/institutions/disciplines. Additionally, the SSHOCro contributes to the level of FAIRness of the data and to the quality of the metadata associated with the datasets.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	SSHOCro aims at providing a semantic interoperability framework for the description of the SSHOC data life cycle in the Social Sciences and the Humanities. In that sense, it can be used as a common language between social sciences and humanities researchers with IT specialists.

Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	The effort to find instances of well documented workflow patterns is huge. In most of the cases, the notion of a workflow remains implicit.
Exploitation plan per partner	<p>FORTH plans to update the SSHOCro with the results of the harmonization with the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SSHOC Marketplace data model. • Conversion Hub data model. • Aioli workflow. <p>and to find contacts and projects for obtaining data from Raman, LIBS Spectrometry, ancient DNA [E-RIHS-GR, HELLAS-CH (IPERION-CH), ARIADNEplus, 4CH</p>

4.3.13. Exploitation –KER #13 ARIADNE-plus

KER Name: ARIADNE-plus Leading partner:UoY- ADS	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	UoY-ADS
Description of the KER	Archaeological data management best practice guidance developed within E-RIHS and SSHOC will be implemented within the ARIADNEplus infrastructure and workflow, which may then be made available as a service within SSHOC.
Value Proposition for end-user communities	Archaeological researchers generate data with natural science methods on a wide range of artefacts, biological remains and physical materials. Therefore, data management best practice guidance is very valuable for researchers in archaeology as well as in other fields of study where such work is being carried out.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	Research infrastructures can support data-centric workflows by providing templates and services for best practice documentation, curation and use of FAIR scientific data. EOSC will become the central hub for research infrastructure services supporting the European Commission’s FAIR data and Open Science policies. SSHOC, E-RIHS, ARIADNE-plus and other research infrastructure projects are committed to share various services through EOSC. These will include ARIADNEplus data management services which will be relevant for researchers in different fields of study.

Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	Researchers in archaeology, heritage science and other humanities generating and/or using scientific data. Main needs are guidance and services for reliable and effective management and sharing of data complying with FAIR data and Open Science policies. The best practice services shared through EOSC generally are Cloud-based web services.
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	The main impediment for full exploitation, i.e. widest possible use, is many researchers still not familiar with FAIR data and Open Science practices.
Exploitation plan per partner	ADS: Promote ARIADNE within the archaeological community, and more widely within SSHOC and EOSC.

4.3.14. Exploitation – KER #14 Knowledge Graphs in Electoral Studies to bring together structured and unstructured data

KER Name: Knowledge Graphs in Electoral Studies to bring together structured and unstructured data Leading partner: UNOTT	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	AUSSDA, UNIVIE, SWC
Description of the KER	The Electoral Studies Knowledge Graph Pilot provides a web-based knowledge and information discovery application for professionals and scientists in the field of electoral studies. Based on a comprehensive Knowledge Graph on Electoral Studies (a Knowledge Graph is a knowledge base that is enriched with data and documents that are interlinked with each other based on the underlying knowledge model ⁵) the user can search and explore for relevant information - in the pilot system: research methods, research concepts, and publications - in one single point of access instead of time consuming searching and browsing inside of several information and data repositories.
Value Proposition for end-user communities	Single point of access to relevant information and data in the field of electoral studies. Such information and data is usually not easy to find and scattered over dozens of sources to be identified and analysed. Thereby time and efforts can be saved for researchers and practitioners in the field.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	The Electoral Studies Knowledge Graph Pilot demonstrates and showcases the potential of Knowledge Graphs used in the field of social science and thereby EOSC - here more concrete in electoral studies - for improved and easy-to-use information retrieval. Thereby interconnections in the research area are made explicit, and users save time and efforts to find and make use of relevant data and information for their research activities.

⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Knowledge_graph.

Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	The application is a web-based tool that is publicly available. Target groups are researchers and practitioners in the field of electoral studies worldwide.
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	Continuous and frequent promotion is needed to the specified end user communities. Barriers: no continuous maintenance of infrastructure, application and data. Too little end community support to make best
Exploitation plan per partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UNOTT: Partner name + plan • AUSSDA: Partner name + plan • UNIVIE: Partner name + plan • SWC: will use this as a demonstrator to showcase the use of knowledge graphs to find and use data in the field of electoral studies quickly and easily and well organised in a single point of access. The application is maintained by SWC for the full project period and at least for additional 6 months after the SSHOC project period, and will be used continuously for demonstration purposes to potential customers and partners.

4.3.15. Exploitation –KER #15 Ethnic and Migrant Minority Survey

Registry

KER Name: Ethnic and Migrant Minority Survey Registry Leading partner: Sciences Po	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	From SSHOC: Sciences Po Outside of SSHOC: COST Action 16111 - ETHMIGSURVEYDATA, FAIRETHMIGQUANT (ANR-funded project)
Description of the KER	<p>The Ethnic and Migrant Minorities (EMM) Survey Registry is a free online discovery tool and database that displays detailed information (i.e. metadata) about existing quantitative sample-based surveys conducted with EMM populations in Europe.</p> <p>Jointly developed by SSHOC, the COST Action 16111 – ETHMIGSURVEYDATA (a network of 200+ EMM researchers across Europe), and a French Agence Nationale de la Recherche (ANR)-funded project, FAIRETHMIGQUANT, the EMM Survey Registry promotes the FAIR principles and provides a concrete example of how an interdisciplinary data community can drive the creation of a FAIR-friendly tool for the social sciences using a bottom up, collaborative approach for the benefit of a wide range of stakeholders.</p> <p>The EMM Survey Registry is intended for use by researchers, policymakers, and other practitioners in their own research and/or policy-related activities. As a model of co-creation, it will be of interest to data communities committed to making their data FAIR, to data curation actors looking to partner or connect with data producers or users for whom they can tailor their current data curation services, and to policy-makers working on open research and open data initiatives.</p>

<p>Value Proposition for end-user communities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The metadata offered by the EMM Survey Registry improves how researchers, policymakers, and other practitioners can discover, learn from, and/or reuse existing quantitative survey research on EMMs integration and inclusion. • The EMM Survey Registry is a model for other data communities interested in setting up their own service. aimed at making their research data 'FAIR' • The EMM Survey Registry (via it's back-end: https://registry.ethmigsurveydatahub.eu/nova/login) offers data producers with a free platform to showcase their research.
<p>Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The EMM Survey Registry is an innovative service, as it has been designed by the data community itself as a means to make their research data 'FAIR.' As such, the EMM Survey Registry serves as concrete evidence to EOSC and other Open Science/Data policy initiatives that data communities can adopt and promote the 'FAIR' principles if provided with appropriate or sufficient funding and support (which was the case for the ethnic and migration studies data community due to SSHOC, ETHMIGSURVEYDATA, and FAIRETHMIGQUANT). • The EMM Survey Registry can motivate existing and new members of the ethnic and migration studies data community to make their research data FAIR, especially as the service itself can be used freely to showcase existing research.
<p>Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The front-end of the EMM Survey Registry (direct link: https://registry.ethmigsurveydatahub.eu/) is where all the metadata is made freely available for discovery, access, and re-use. The metadata, which are provided on a survey-by-survey basis, are detailed and well-structured. Moreover, the metadata are easy to exploit and leverage due to the user-friendly interface and functionalities of the front-end. • The back-end of the EMM Survey Registry (https://registry.ethmigsurveydatahub.eu/nova/login) is where the metadata are managed and where new metadata can be directly contributed to the EMM Survey Registry for free. Administrators of the EMM Survey Registry have full access to the back-end, meaning they can use the full range of management functionalities. For all other users, access is restricted in 2 ways: (1) they need to be approved for and issued an account by the administrators of the EMM Survey Registry and (2) if authorised to access the back-end, they will only have partial access (i.e. only being able to access functionalities that allow them to contribute new metadata to the EMM Survey Registry).
<p>Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • After funding for SSHOC, ETHMIGSURVEYDATA, and FAIRETHMIGQUANT end, the Sciences Po team will need new funding streams to continue its ongoing dissemination and exploitation efforts. • For the metadata offerings of the EMM Survey Registry to remain current and relevant, data producers need to contribute new metadata. It is possible that for some data producers contributing new metadata about their research to the EMM Survey Registry is not a high priority (e.g. limited human resources which need to be allocated to research).

Exploitation plan per partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sciences Po: Online and in-person outreach about the EMM Survey Registry and its metadata to different user communities (i.e. data producers, data users, data curators, data managers).
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4.3.16. Exploitation –KER #16 [MCSQ]: The Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires

KER Name: [MCSQ]: The Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires Leading partner: ESS ERIC	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	ESS ERIC (UPF)
Description of the KER	<p>MCSQ is a multilingual corpus compiled from questionnaires from the ESS, the EVS, SHARE and WIZ in (British) English source language and their translations into Catalan, Czech, French, German, Norwegian, Portuguese, Spanish, Russian, as well as 29 language varieties (e.g., Swiss-French, Austrian-German). It is freely accessible through an interface. Datasets can be customised and downloaded. The corpus is sentence aligned with respect to the source and allows for the possibility of creating translation memories.</p> <p>The MCSQ functions both as a repository of previous rounds of survey texts and a tool for systematic analysis of previous translation decisions. Before the compilation of the MCSQ, no method for tracing translation decisions systematically in multilingual surveys has been in place.</p>
Value Proposition for end-user communities	MCSQ can be used by social scientists, translators, linguists, researchers of different fields and other interested parties. The main characteristics of the corpus are (1) multilingualism. The corpus includes 9 languages and 29 language varieties making it highly relevant for minority language surveys. (2) comparability: It is possible to visualise and analyze translation decisions across languages.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	In line with the EOSC objectives and FAIR principles, this corpus is an open-source and open-access research resource. It contributes to the consolidation and the improvement of the translation procedures in multilingual survey projects by providing an open, searchable, aligned and annotated corpus of such questionnaires. Overall the MCSQ facilitates a more scientific approach to survey translation and research.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	MCSQ can be used by social scientists, translators, linguists, researchers of different fields and other interested parties. The database is accessed by end-users interface available at https://www.upf.edu/web/mcsq .
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	The interface of the tool can be improved, UI/UX engineer work is needed. MCSQ's 3rd (entitled Rosalind Franklin) version with more data, new annotations and new interface functionalities was released in August 2021. Soon, the corpus will be submitted for permanent archiving in CLARIN.

Exploitation plan per partner	<p>ESS ERIC (UPF)</p> <p>After development is finished and the SSHOC ends, the MCSQ interface and database will be maintained for two years, during this time, the MCSQ team will work on increasing its visibility in the SSHOC community. The MCSQ will also increase its usage when the different survey projects start translating new questionnaires and use it to retrieve past translations. The first presentations in the ESS National Coordinator's Forum and in the Core Scientific Team meetings in November 2020 were planned to increase internal usage of the tool, and have been successful in adding new users. A series of presentations of the final tool will be proposed to all survey projects' stakeholders (ESS, EVS, SHARE, WageIndicator).</p>
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4.3.17. Exploitation –KER #17 Repository service for SSH (Dataverse)

KER Name: Repository service for SSH (Dataverse) Leading partner: KNAW (DANS)	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	KNAW (DANS), AUSSDA, PSNC, University of Tromso, UGOE, CNR
Description of the KER	<p>The repository service for SSH is built upon the community-driven open source Dataverse software.</p> <p>Its modular design facilitates integration with other data services such as DataCite or ROpenSci, CLARIN's Language Resource Switchboard, and supports the development of additional functionality and services.</p> <p>Two types of services are being developed:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A central (ERIC-level) service in the cloud, adapted to the needs of the relevant European SSH community, for small institutes to have a research data repository for their designated community. 2. An 'Archive in a box' software installation package, an adapted version to the needs of the European SSH community with documentation, for downloading and usage in their own environment by institutes themselves.
Value Proposition for end-user communities	Both types of service can be used by research institutes and data centres to share and publish research data during and after a research project.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	The Dataverse software makes it easily possible to publish research data FAIR. It promotes the open science movement and stimulates researchers to publish and share their data.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	Dataverse has an easy to use User Interface and makes depositing of data for researchers who would like to publish and share their data according to the FAIR principles very easy.

Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	Task 5.2 will deliver the adapted software with documentation, but the deployment of the services has to be done by research Infrastructures, research institutes or data centres themselves. Both types of services have their own requirements in terms of staffing and infrastructure. All developed functionality is open source.
Exploitation plan per partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KNAW (DANS) will use the developed functionality for their new data stations and DataverseNL. • AUSSDA will use it for the upgrade of their repository. • The same for University of Tromso and UGOE. • Negotiations are currently underway with CESSDA, DARIAH and CLARIN to see whether a central service on the level of the ERIC will be useful for smaller institutes.

4.3.18. Exploitation –KER #18 ADS Guides to Good Practice

KER Name: ADS Guides to Good Practice Leading partner: UoY-ADS	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	UoY-ADS
Description of the KER	The ADS Guides to Good Practice represent the international standard for archaeological data management best practice. The Guides incorporate the understanding developed around archaeological data from the wide range of EC research projects, and can be a resource within EOSC for SSH data management.
Value Proposition for end-user communities	Archaeological researchers generate data with natural science methods on a wide range of artefacts, biological remains and physical materials. Therefore, data management best practice guidance is very valuable for researchers in archaeology as well as in other fields of study where such work is being carried out. The Guides have been developed over 25 years with input, updates and case studies from across Europe.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	The Guides were developed to support archaeological data creators, but reflect best practice for SSH data, supporting participation in EOSC.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	Target users are archaeologists and any other SSH researchers needing to manage a wide range of data types. The Guides are freely and openly available at https://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gpwiki/ .
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	The Guides have undergone continual updates over the last 25 years, and as a core service of ADS, will continue to be updated.
Exploitation plan per partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UoY-ADS: Promote the Guides to Good Practice within the archaeological community, and more widely within SSHOC and EOSC.

4.3.19. Exploitation –KER #19 Multilingual Terminologies

KER Name: Multilingual Terminologies Leading partners: CNR	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	CNR (CLARIN-IT)
Description of the KER	<p>A set of multilingual metadata is provided by using Machine Translation services with human validation, with attention for highly specialised sectors.</p> <p>Multilingual terminologies are created collecting standards and other technical documents on Data Stewardship and extracting terms with NLP techniques. For each term a definition is also collected. The collected terms are used to enrich other existing terminologies, and to Loterre Open Science Thesaurus. Validated terms, their definitions are translated using MT translation services and their translations will be made available as SKOS resources.</p>
Value Proposition for end-user communities	The lack of multilingual terminological resources in different domains constitutes an obstacle to the access and reuse of information. Multilingual metadata and vocabularies are meant to provide multilingual access to content across different languages and improve discovery by non-native speakers.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	Multilingual terminologies are developed to support better discovery and access to SSH content and are provided as FAIR resources in line with EOSC principles.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	Target users are any SSH researchers needing to manage a wide range of SSH content. The resources are freely and openly available. The vocabularies will be findable through the VLO and other CLARIN services.
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	In order to maximise findability and hence usability and exploitation, if appropriate, the vocabularies will be made available through the Vocabulary Commons.
Exploitation plan per partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CNR-ILC and CLARIN-IT will provide the multilingual terminologies through the ILC4CLARIN datacentre, the national node of CLARIN-IT (Italian CLARIN-B centre of the CLARIN-ERIC infrastructure) and, additionally, will make them available as SKOS resources. • OEAW as host of the SSH Vocabulary Commons service will publish the vocabularies SKOS versions.

4.3.20. Exploitation –KER #20 surveycodings.org

KER Name: surveycodings.org Leading partner: SHARE/ Centerdata	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	EVS, Centerdata, GESIS, WageIndicator.
Description of the KER	Surveycodings offers a host of social science codings measuring individual and socio-economic variables. The developed tools consist of a multilingual repository containing questionnaires, data collection tools, and coding frames based on standard statistical classifications covering a large number of countries. The variables included within the project are the following: occupation, industry, levels and fields of education, region, food groups, religions, cost of living, and marital status, all coded according to ruling standards. The benefits of such a tool are 1) reduced manual post-coding, 2) less harmonisation logistics, and 3) decreased costs by linking survey questionnaires to databases to allow the coding of survey variables during the interview.
Value Proposition for end-user communities	Surveycodings is a free service geared towards social science projects, data archives, researchers and any interested parties. The available coding sets use standard classifications to organize and code information. These coding sets can be employed for input harmonization at the data collection stage, resulting in more consistent data that enable cross-national data collection. Also, the codings can be used as a resource for post-coding the open-ended questions during survey processing before its final release. In computer-assisted surveys the coding sets will be ready to use for respondent's self-selection, as well as interviewer's selection.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	Surveycodings is a valuable tool meant to facilitate the research within the social surveys endeavour by shrinking costs and logistics associated with input and output harmonization of survey data. The supply of the developed tools will occur following the FAIR principles promoted within EOSC.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	Surveycodings web page provides 1) a database live search for each variable, 2) a demo questionnaire including all variables, 3) database lookups for single countries, 4) the download of coding sets, questionnaires, and 5) the possibility to link certain coding sets.
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	The surveycodings project is being developed under the SSHOC grant. The end of the SSHOC project poses challenges related to the maintenance, update and expansion of SurveyCodings.

Exploitation plan per partner	<p>EVS - TiU The EVS team is responsible for the building of the religious denominations coding sets. Along with that it oversees the workflow timeline, maintains the internal communication, works on the visibility and dissemination campaign.</p> <p>Centerdata The Centerdata team is in charge of the technical aspects of the platform (webpage set-up, development of tools etc.).</p> <p>GESIS The GESIS team works on the construction and updating of the coding sets regarding fields and levels of education.</p> <p>WageIndicator The WageIndicator team's tasks regard the processing of occupations, industry and region coding frames.</p>
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4.3.21. Exploitation –KER #21 RESTORE

KER Name: RESTORE Leading partner: CNR	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	The RESTORE development is coordinated by the CNR - OVI Institute with co-funding from the Regione Toscana, in the context of the call POR-FSE 2014-20. The approach, the software components and the technological solutions developed for the RESTORE project are seen as achievements and by-products provided by the SSHOC T9.4, which was in charge of developing the digital infrastructure needed.
Description of the KER	<p>RESTORE releases a digital platform for mapping, integration and reuse of heterogeneous datasets, focusing on the recovery, integration, accessibility and reuse of digital resources, provided by GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums) institutions, research centres and conservation laboratories. Materials are collected, mapped, transformed and stored for access and reuse, according to the CIDOC-CRM ontology.</p> <p>http://dev.restore.ovi.cnr.it/ [date of access: 03.08.2021]</p>
Value Proposition for end-user communities	<p>RESTORE proposes a virtuous model of integration, management, display, reuse and sustainability of data, with a full selection and documentation of tools that work for each standardised and validated procedure within the different fields of knowledge. The model also makes use of open access sources, following FAIR protocols.</p> <p>The targeted communities are GLAM institutions and research centres, i.e. National and International Archives, Museums, Libraries. The RESTORE digitised materials conform to the data and information standards actually in use, EAD/EAC-CFP, ICCD, TEI, among others, in the Cultural heritage domain; finally, these different cataloguing systems are made interoperable.</p>

<p>Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context</p>	<p>The platform elaborates a sustainable workflow, together with a toolkit supporting data management and integration of heterogeneous resources - from ingestion, to publication, through processing. In fact, the pipeline is currently clearly designed and supported by a set of open access tools.</p> <p>The project's future empowerment focuses on the Heritage Science data integration, with the ingestion of datasets coming from the E-RIHS conservation labs and institutes internationally (especially, MOLAB and DIGILAB); the development will lead, therefore, to the creation of a cross-disciplinary information integration system and a suite of open access tools for data FAIRification.</p>
<p>Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool</p>	<p>In terms of user communities, the task pilot involves people and datasets coming from the following institutions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Archives (Prato State Archives). • Museums (Museo di Palazzo Pretorio, Prato). • OVI (Istituto Opera del Vocabolario Italiano) – CNR (IT). • Cultural Heritage Superintendencies (The Archival and Bibliographic Superintendency). • Coordination Agencies (Central Institute for the Union Catalogue of Italian Libraries, ICCU). • Multiple research institutes in the field of Heritage Science and SSH, both within academic departments or research infrastructures active at a national level. <p>RESTORE allows users to merge and map their historical digitised datasets and original sources to get a full picture of a given historical period, that can be eventually stored and browsed by means of querying (through a SPARQL Endpoint) and of a semantic structure based on people-events-places. Furthermore, the platform supports the maintenance of the original sources and offers a web browsing tool of the data (LODview).</p>
<p>Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The RESTORE modular architecture uses in part custom components to perform the data conversion from the provided standard sources and, therefore, needs adaptation of the custom parsers to the incoming datasets. - The platform is released in its alpha version (tester) for the SSHOC project, therefore its beta release and the full user-friendly interface will regard further developments of the project itself.
<p>Exploitation plan per partner</p>	<p>Regione Toscana (Together with the following partners: Prato State Archives, Museo di Palazzo Pretorio - Prato, The Tuscan Archival and Bibliographic Superintendency, Central Institute for the Union Catalogue of Italian Libraries - ICCU + "DATINI pilot";</p>

4.3.22. Exploitation –KER #22 Dataset: investigating the effects of machine translation and post-editing in survey translation

KER Name: Dataset: investigating the effects of machine translation and post-editing in survey translation Leading Partner: ESS	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	ESS/GESIS, ESS/UPF
Description of the KER	Dataset of two experiments in the language pairs English-Russian, English-German. The dataset contains linguistic data (Segments translated in different methods) and human data (participants filled in questionnaires). The dataset contains translation versions across different steps of a team translation approach.
Value Proposition for end-user communities	This dataset can be used by social scientists, translators, linguists, researchers of different fields and other interested parties. It is the first open-access dataset on experimental research assessing for the effects of machine translation and post-editing in team translation of survey questionnaires.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	In line with the EOSC objectives and FAIR principles, this dataset is an open-source and open-access research resource. It contributes to the consolidation and the improvement of the translation procedures in multilingual survey projects by providing a dataset that other researchers can exploit to better understand the implications of new trends in translation practice.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	Linguists, translators, social scientists, researchers in these fields.
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	Knowledge of the dataset, dissemination.
Exploitation plan per partner	The dataset is being cleaned and prepared to be deposited in a CEESDA/GESIS repository.

4.3.23. Exploitation - KER #23a Improved and FAIR data Repositories - New ESS data repository

KER Name: Improved and FAIR data Repositories - New ESS data repository Leading partner: ESS	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	NSD (ESS ERIC)
Description of the KER	ESS data and documentation available to users from the new repository accompanied by interoperable services.

Value Proposition for end-user communities	New interoperable ESS data services for new uses and new types of users.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	ESS data can be combined with other types of data from various domains by aggregation to the same regional levels. Data are relevant for various types of users including for policy makers.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	Target users: new and existing ESS users. Use of the service/tool: The new repository will allow for more flexible use for data users and curators.
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	Not that we are aware of. The services will be offered as part of the ESS ERIC infrastructure.
Exploitation plan per partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The NSD archive team (ESS ERIC) will use the ESS website and newsletter to target ESS users. • NSD and ESS ERIC will contribute towards making the new services known to (potential) EOSC data users through our social media channels.

4.3.24. Exploitation - KER #23b Improved and FAIR data Repositories - SSHOC Trusted Repositories

KER Name: Improved and FAIR data Repositories - SSHOC Trusted Repositories Leading partner: CESSDA	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	CESSDA/FSD, DARIAH-PSNC, CLARIN ERIC, KNAW(DANS), CESSDA/SND, CESSDA/UKDA, CNR

<p>Description of the KER</p>	<p>SSHOC promotes trust and quality assurance by supporting data repositories in their journey to CoreTrustSeal certification.</p> <p>Fourteen data repositories were selected for certification support through an open call between June and August 2020. These repositories are in varying stages of preparation with some closer to being ready to apply for certification and others more focused on taking note of issues and establishing best practices. The work of the SSHOC certification task team is to meet repositories at their point of readiness and provide assistance and guidance related to the certification process along with feedback on the repositories' self-assessments before they submit their applications to CoreTrustSeal.</p> <p>SSHOC works in cooperation with FAIRsFAIR and with other EOSC projects which also have activities to support the certification of data repositories. FAIRsFAIR, for instance, aims to align the FAIR Principles with the CoreTrustSeal requirements. The EOSC Executive Board FAIR Working Group has published <i>Recommendations on certifying services required to enable FAIR within EOSC</i>.</p> <p>Supported repositories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CLARIN-LV • Corpus OVI dell'italiano antico • Croatian Social Science Data Archive (CROSSDA) • DAIS - Digital Archive of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts • DARIAH-DE Repository • Digital Library of University of Maribor • Digital Repository of Scientific Institutes • Historic Graves • Lithuanian Data Archive for Social Sciences and Humanities (LiDA) • mdw Repository • NAKALA • SB/CLARIN Repository (Språkbanken Text CLARIN Repository) • Sciences Po, Center for Socio-Political Data (CDSP) • Slovak Archive of Social Data (SASD)
<p>Value Proposition for end-user communities</p>	<p>In addition to supporting the selected 14 repositories in their certification process, we explore the benefits and criticisms of CoreTrustSeal certification and certification in general and provide CoreTrustSeal feedback on its requirements based on the lessons learned from support work.</p> <p>CoreTrustSeal is not directly suitable for all repositories but is often used as the starting point (e.g. <i>Turning FAIR into Reality</i> report), which is why we explore the common features and differences of various SSH repositories to examine its applicability to them.</p> <p>Certification improves the practices of repositories and trusted digital repositories enable access to FAIR data over time. Certification contributes to providing access to secure and trusted repositories by identifying these to researchers, funders and other stakeholders.</p>

<p>Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context</p>	<p>Certification and trust work promotes open science and contributes to the increased visibility of data to the scientific community.</p> <p>Certification also encompasses and promotes FAIR data and principles. Certified Trusted Digital Repositories play a key part in a FAIR ecosystem comprising FAIR Digital Objects. It is recommended that FAIR data be stored in certified repositories to ensure their long-term access. (<i>TFIR</i> report).</p> <p>SSHOC Trusted Repositories collaborates with EOSC Nordic and FAIRsFAIR in outlining a common trust approach for SSH. The support in achieving certification provided by SSHOC and other sources has the potential to be extended and expanded through the development of a community of TDRs. The ongoing trend for consolidation of and interoperability between actors in the research data lifecycle is exemplified in Europe by the development of the EOSC, although the demand for high quality data and metadata that aligns with the FAIR principles is global. Throughout the Turning FAIR into Reality report, TDRs are acknowledged as key (meta)data hubs as dependencies for a range of interoperable services. Active preservation ensures that (meta) data assets retain their FAIRness and their value over time.</p>
<p>Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool</p>	<p>Target users include trusted data repositories and repositories seeking certification, researchers looking to access and deposit data as well as research funders and other stakeholders seeking information on trustworthy repositories.</p>
<p>Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players</p>	<p>The certification process requires engagement from data repositories. Not recognising the benefits of certification or only focusing on its challenges may lead to lack of engagement. This can be combatted by continued awareness of the certification benefits, future cooperation between repositories, a wider trust framework and going beyond national service providers and Europe. As there is no single certification that suits all repositories, the existing certification framework should be updated to respond to the needs of diverse repositories.</p> <p>These activities are outside the scope of the SSHOC project and require additional resources, but the experiences gained here lay the groundwork for further steps in certification and setting up a wider trust framework. FAIRsFAIR project is suggesting creating a European network of TDRs and SSHOC should collaborate with them. It is expected that the ERICs would be interested in such collaboration and Task 8.2 has sent them a survey to find out about their interest. The results will be reported in D8.3.</p>
<p>Exploitation plan per partner</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See above. • DARIAH: UGOE/ CLARIAH-DE as provider of the CTS certified DARIAH-DE repository and the CTS certified TextGrid repository will be available for future consultations and cooperations and promotes the CTS in the German-language communities.

4.3.25. Exploitation - KER #23c Improved and FAIR data Repositories - SHARE survey data

KER Name: Improved and FAIR data Repositories - SHARE survey data Leading partner: SHARE	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	CentERdata
Description of the KER	Technological development continues to offer ways of health data collection that go beyond asking survey questions. Such new types of data were collected in the SHARE survey by means of Dried Blood Spot Samples (DBSS) and accelerometer data. These data demand new data protection rules and must often be extensively processed, validated and calibrated before they can be made accessible. SHARE and CentERdata develop a strategy to give access to such data according to FAIR principles.
Value Proposition for end-user communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers: Seamless access to high quality research data. • Research & e-Infrastructures: Common policies on: FAIR. • Universities & Research Performing Organisations: data which is easily repurposed and reusable across disciplines. • Civil Society and Citizen Scientists: Opportunities to participate in scientific progress via open access to SSH data, services and tools.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	The DBSS and accelerometer data collected in SHARE are an example for successful linkage of biomedical data to SSH survey data. Guidelines for the collection, processing, and access of biomedical data in SSH are provided.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	Research infrastructures that collect biomedical data can build upon the measures taken in SHARE to assure meeting ethical requirements and publishing the data according to FAIR principles.
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	Ethical regulations of the collection, storage, and analysis of biomedical data might differ by countries which leads to additional measures and/or approvals that might be necessary.
Exploitation plan per partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SHARE: ethical measures were already taken in the collection of DBSS and accelerometer data. • SHARE and CentERdata: Data access plan for biomedical data is already in use by the SHARE download portal run by CentERdata. First Accelerometer data is already published, DBSS data will be published in the future

4.3.26. Exploitation - KER #24a SSH Communities - SSH Training Community

KER Name: SSH Training Community Leading partner: KNAW (DANS)	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	LIBER, CESSDA/GESIS, KNAW (DANS), DARIAH
Description of the KER	<p>The SSHOC Training Community was launched in September 2019 and currently numbers more than 157 members from 43 countries.</p> <p>The SSH Training Community is a worldwide community of trainers who collaborate to improve our professional capabilities by sharing their expertise and resources.</p> <p>The focus is on trainers serving the Social Sciences and Humanities communities. Community's activities are centred around tools and services which are offered through the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and are valuable for SSH trainers.</p> <p>By bringing together experts from multiple disciplines, the community is looking to create synergies and exploit the collective knowledge and skills for mutual benefit.</p>
Value Proposition for end-user communities	<p>Member Benefits:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monthly community calls where members exchange and discuss topics of interest. • Opportunities to create new training materials to support and enhance the use of SSH tools and services. • A guaranteed inclusion in the international SSH Trainer Directory which will increase individual visibility. • Preferential access to Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps, and to workshops, webinars and conferences organised by WP6 T6.5. • A standing invitation to contribute personal resources to the SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit and advice on improvements. • Exclusive access to a communal mailing list and Google drive to facilitate networking and information sharing with peers.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	Bringing together trainers and training coordinators raises the awareness of what is happening within EOSC, enables overall knowledge exchange and efficient organisation of training, reuse of existing training materials and the co-creation of training materials.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	The community acts as a community of practice for SSH trainers and training coordinators in EOSC. The members are from different organisations but all provide and/or coordinate training related to EOSC.
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	The community can be continued without much effort nor barriers. Whether the group can continue as subgroup of the Community of Practice of training coordinators is being considered.

Exploitation plan per partner	Possibilities of sustaining the community after the project are currently being investigated (as mentioned under “potential barriers”). Depending on the outcome, partners can use the community to engage with other trainers and exchange knowledge and information.
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4.3.27. Exploitation - KER #24b SSH Communities - Ethnic Minorities and Migration Data Community

KER Name: Ethnic Minorities and Migration Data Community Leading partner: Sciences Po	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	Sciences Po
Description of the KER	<p>One research group of interest to SSHOC is a data community undertaking research on ethnic and migration studies.</p> <p>Led by Prof Laura Morales (Sciences Po) with support from Ami Saji and a small team of junior researchers and research assistants, a SSHOC task group is working to improve how quantitative survey data on ethnic and migrant minorities (EMMs) can be shared with and discovered by a wide range of users in Europe and beyond.</p> <p>This task group is also working hand in hand with two closely related projects, COST Action 16111 – ETHMIGSURVEYDATA, (a research network with 200 plus members who are primarily based in Europe, and are part of the ethnic and migration studies field) and FAIRETHMIGQUANT, (a project funded via the French Agence Nationale de la Recherche Open Science call).</p>
Value Proposition for end-user communities	This data community brings together all diverse types of stakeholders of quantitative survey data on EMMs’ integration and/or inclusion. Together, it has successfully developed and deployed a variety of resources aimed at making their data ‘FAIR,’ most notably the EMM Survey Registry. As such, this data community serves as a salient and cogent example of why and how end-users should collaborate and work jointly to develop resources that help to render the data they are interested in ‘FAIR.’
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	This data community has thus far successfully developed and launched the EMM Survey Registry, a free online tool that facilitates the discovery of quantitative surveys on EMMs’ integration and/or inclusion. The process and strategy used by this data community to develop the EMM Survey Registry can therefore serve as a blueprint for other data communities (even beyond SSH disciplines) looking to develop their own FAIR-aligned tools. Moreover, as the data community is a model of co-creation and co-generation, it could also be a source of inspiration for data curation actors across Europe (and beyond) looking to partner or connect with data producers or users for whom they can tailor their current data curation services, as well as for policy-makers working on open research and open data initiatives.

Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	The operational model of the data community, as well as its outputs (i.e. the resources it has produced, like the EMM Survey Registry), can be replicated by other data communities (even beyond SSH disciplines).
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	The main projects funding this data community will conclude in 2022. Therefore, new funding sources are needed to fully sustain and continue the scientific work undertaken by this data community.
Exploitation plan per partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sciences Po: Regular outreach via different communication channels/settings to showcase the data community itself and its various outputs

4.3.28. Exploitation - KER #24c SSH Communities - Election Studies Data Community

Individual exploitation plan upcoming in the next iteration of the exploitation plan.

KER Name: Election Studies Data Community Leading partner: UNOTT	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	
Description of the KER	
Value Proposition for end-user communities	
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	
Exploitation plan per partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partner name + plan: Partner name + plan

4.3.29. Exploitation - KER #24d -Heritage Science Data Community

KER Name: Heritage Science Data Community Leading partner: CNR	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	<p>The work performed in terms of data community focus on the integration of datasets coming from the E-RIHS <i>MOLAB</i> testbed, made of those commonly in use in conservation labs and institutes internationally (i.e.: RX, XRF IMAGING, Infrared thermography, XRD - data in the XRDML format-, multispectral information in the ICCD-based format, colorimetry, photographs, radiographs, 3D models, multispectral and raw OCT, TIFF, Raman spectra) together with information coming from GLAMs knowledge base, towards the creation of a cross-disciplinary information integration system and a suite of open access tools for data FAIRification.</p> <p>Materials used and operation criteria (in bullet points):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data and metadata provided by both GLAMs and Research sectors • Different ingestion approaches (OAI-PMH, APIs, dumps, etc) • Different knowledge extraction approaches (NLP, NER, AI) • Different data types represented (3D, 2D and multispectral images, text based documents etc.) • Connections with major EU actors (OpenAire, RDA, EGI, Europeana) • Light technological components, modular approach • Agile development: release quick and often
Description of the KER	<p>Scientists from a range of disciplines – chemists, physicists, material scientists, engineers, archaeologists, digital humanists, conservators, literary scholars, historians and art historians, to name a few - collaborate in the new multidisciplinary field of heritage science. Integrating and sharing data across these fields demonstrates the need for building upon existing data and metadata standards – already developed in each scientific discipline - contributing to, reusing and connecting existing technologies rather than creating new semantic structures, authority tables and linked data.</p>
Value Proposition for end-user communities	<p>The data community performed joint initiatives towards the mapping and pooling of governance related activities across the SSHOC project: e.g.: Task 7.4 Governance: Population, Curation & Sustainability of the SSH Open Marketplace. With regard to the ‘RESTORE pilot’ approach, the technological solutions developed, can be extended to other projects and reused in similar contexts by other institutions within the GLAMs, the Digital Humanities and Heritage Science research communities. Furthermore, the project’s development benefits from the collaboration with DARIAH-ERIC (ESFRI Landmark for the humanities and social sciences) and E-RIHS (ESFRI project for heritage science). In this respect, the development of the RESTORE digital tool aligned with the SSHOC aims to deliver a toolkit for heterogeneous data modelling and integration, as well as to establish a set of good practises for the research data management and storage.</p>

Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	Within the EOSC context, developing a strategic implementation of the SSHOC data integration suite, that should enable: addition of data referencing to the diagnostic operations done on cultural objects considered; accessibility of contents and their contextualization; reuse outside the context of information generation; interoperability between systems; semantic interoperability and context preservation.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	Researchers
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	<p>The ecosystem of digital resources produced by heritage science and cultural heritage communities, though being very broad, often suffers from a high level of fragmentation that, so far, might put at risk its great value's results: quality contents produced by research centres, in addition to being often difficult to find and scarcely accessible, are also characterised by a very low level of interoperability. The tendency is to generate large amounts of digital information. A similar wealth and heterogeneity of information suggests, also in the Cultural Heritage sector, a careful evaluation of the criteria to be used for selecting, structuring, and publishing of data, services and tools of high quality, scientifically validated, which otherwise would remain trapped in the information systems of its creators, often not interoperable and, in some cases, rendered completely inaccessible by the lack of reference standards or of interconversion of the reference domain standards.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited respect to platforms (MOLAB) • Limited respect to new developments • Limited respect to the number of analytical techniques covered (RFX) • Still limited respect to the number of data types considered (from the HS point of view)
Exploitation plan per partner	<p>MOLAB testbed: contextual data provided by CNR-OVI and CNR-ISPC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISPC: OAI_DC XML records, harvested through OAI-PMH , PDF files of the Journal Issues • OVI: text-based resources, tagged textual corpora, vocabularies and dictionaries, archival descriptions (XML-EAD), EAC authority files

4.3.30. Exploitation - KER #24e SSH Communities - Religious Studies (RESILIENCE) Data Community

<p>KER Name: Religious Studies (RESILIENCE) Data Community Leading partner: INFAl, FSCIRE</p>	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	Fscire, InfAl

Description of the KER	RESILIENCE will bring in its specificities for scholars working on Religious Studies, including its unique focus on both physical and digital aspects of Religious Studies, spanning also its attempt to build bridges in between them. By its focus on Religious Studies, RESILIENCE is complementary to the work of SSHOC and forms the thematic community of “(Digital) Religious Studies”, being able to fulfil the specific aspirations of other stakeholders not directly being addressed by SSHOC. More collaboration possibilities are foreseen in the future, for example around the formation of thematic communities related to Religious Studies concerning data management, and the training programme.
Value Proposition for end-user communities	SSHOC offers RESILIENCE access to a marketplace tailored for the SSH domain which has synergies with the RESILIENCE service suite, as well as access to Open Science best practices, and to FAIR research data.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	RESILIENCE is filling the gap in the ERA and SSHOC on Religious Studies.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	Mostly academics.
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	No.
Exploitation plan per partner	Not applicable.

4.3.31. Exploitation - KER #24f SSH Communities - Historic Economic (EURHISFIRM) Data Community

KER Name: Historic Economic (EURHISFIRM) Data Community Leading partner: EEP PSE, SAFE, UANTWERP	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	EEP PSE, SAFE, Uantwep
Description of the KER	EURHISFIRM “Historical high-quality company-level data for Europe” was a design study to build a world-class research infrastructure (RI) compliant to the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) data principles. The project aimed to increase the accessibility and usability of historical company-level data (financial, governance, and geographical) and to expand the available pool of this data.

Value Proposition for end-user communities	The EURHISFIRM project was conceived to address the current lack of high quality long-term empirical European data that prevents the usage and testing of models for analysing structural and cyclical changes, which are crucial for understanding the interactions between financial, economic, and social evolutions.
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	EURHISFIRM participates in the EOSC ecosystem via integration into SSHOC as a consortium member addressing the need for historical company-level data.
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	Targets users range from academics, businesses, to policy makers; and more generally to anyone with an interest in historical company-level data.
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	The design phase of EURHISFIRM has reached its conclusion, more information can be found on the website of the project: https://eurhisfirm.eu .
Exploitation plan per partner	The design phase of EURHISFIRM has reached its conclusion, more information can be found on the website of the project: https://eurhisfirm.eu .

4.3.32. Exploitation - KER #24g SSH Communities - Upcoming: Child & Youth Wellbeing (COORDINATE) Data Community

Individual exploitation plan upcoming in the next iteration of the exploitation plan.

KER Name: SSH Communities - Upcoming: Child & Youth Wellbeing (COORDINATE) Data Community Leading partner: NUID UCD, MMU	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	NUID UCD, MMU,
Description of the KER	
Value Proposition for end-user communities	
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	

Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	
Exploitation plan per partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partner name + plan: • Partner name + plan •

4.3.33. Exploitation - KER #25 Audio Survey Experiment

Individual exploitation plan upcoming in the next iteration of the exploitation plan.

KER Name: Audio Survey Experiment Leading partner: NIDI KNAW	
Partners contributing to development, operational and/or training aspects	
Description of the KER	
Value Proposition for end-user communities	
Value proposition for EOSC and the wider policy context	
Target users and needs, including how they use the service/tool	
Potential barriers to exploitation, e.g. lack of update, issues with service providers/other key players	
Exploitation plan per partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partner name + plan: • Partner name + plan •

5. Conclusions and next steps

This Exploitation Plan has considered the work done under WP8, especially Task 8.1 “Governance & Sustainability” (lead CLARIN ERIC) handling the overall governance of the SSHOC project, and the consultation processes conducted among the SSHOC Scientific and Project Management Boards.

The document gives an overview of the joint exploitation paths and the multiple individual plans for the 33 KERs SSHOC has delivered during its funding lifecycle.

As mentioned in section 1, this Exploitation Plan is a living document and will be updated at the end of the project in April 2022 (M40) with the following expected additions:

- Insights from the D8.1 Sustainability Plan.
- Insights from the Tier 1 discussions on the MoU and Sustainability Plan.
- Advancements in the EOSC ecosystem
- Insights from the SSHOC final conference
- Expected TRL levels for KERs
- Update the plan with upcoming individual exploitation plans for KERs Audio Survey Experiment, COORDINATe community and Election Studies Community

6. References

SSHOC Grant Agreement #823782

H2020, Horizon 2020 Annotated Model Grant Agreements,
<https://www.h2020.md/en/horizon-2020-annotated-model-grant-agreements>, retrieved 5/01/2021

EC Europe, Dissemination and Exploitation in Horizon 2020 ,
https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/events/2017-03-01/8_result-dissemination-exploitation.pdf, retrieved 5/01/2021

Clara Petitfils, Suzanne Dumouchel, Nicolas Larrousse, Edward J. Gray, Laure Barbot, Arnaud Roi, Matej Ďurčo, Klaus Illmayer, Stefan Buddenbohm, & Tomasz Parkola. (2021). *D7.5 Marketplace - Governance*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5608487>

Marieke Willems, Tracey Biller, Filomena Minichiello, & Veronika Heider. (2021). *SSHOC D2.2 Preliminary Report on User Communities' Engagement (V1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4655994>

